

Extracting the temperature dependence of both nanowire resistivity and junction resistance from electrical measurements on printed silver nanowire networks

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ABSTRACT

Printed networks of nanoparticles (e.g. nanodots, nanowires, nanosheets) are important for a range of electronic, sensing and energy storage applications. Characterising the temperature dependence of both the nanoparticle resistivity (ρ_{NW}) and inter-particle junction resistance (R_J) in such networks is crucial for understanding the conduction mechanism and so for optimising network properties. However, it is challenging to extract both ρ_{NW} and R_J from standard electrical measurements. Here, using silver nanowires (AgNWs) as a model system, we describe a broadly applicable method to extract both parameters from resistivity measurements on nanowire networks. We achieve this by combining a simple theoretical model with temperature-dependent resistivity measurements on sets of networks fabricated from nanowires of different lengths. As expected, our results demonstrate that R_J is the predominant bottleneck for charge transport within these networks, with R_{NW}/R_J in the range 0.03-0.7. We demonstrate that the temperature dependence of ρ_{NW} exhibits characteristic Bloch-Grüneisen behaviour, yielding a Debye temperature between 133-181K, which aligns with reported values for individual nanowires. Likewise, our findings for residual resistivity and electron-phonon coupling constants closely match published values measured on individual nanowires. The junction resistance also follows Bloch-Grüneisen behaviour with similar parameters, indicating the junctions consist of metallic silver. These findings confirm the validity of our method and provide a deeper insight into the conduction mechanisms in AgNW networks. They also pave the way toward simultaneous measurement of ρ_{NW} and R_J in other important systems, notably carbon nanotube networks.

Keywords: Nanowires; nanotubes; solution-deposited; conductivity; inter-particle.

INTRODUCTION

The ability to solution-deposit electronic devices, components and circuitry has led to the rapidly expanding field of printed electronics (PE). Although printed electronics devices tend to have reduced performance compared to traditional electronics, they display considerable advantages in terms of flexibility, area-scalability, and cost effectiveness.^{1, 2} Due to their combination of solution-processability and their excellent electrical performance, a range of nanoparticles - including 0D nanodots, 1D nanowires/nanotubes and 2D nanosheets - have been extensively explored in a range of PE applications.^{1, 3-5} Printed materials and additive manufacturing has become a large area of recent interest⁶⁻⁸ and in particular printed nanoparticle networks have been heavily studied for highly conductive transparent electrodes⁹ and photodetectors.¹⁰ Alternatively, metallic nanowire networks have shown promise as flexible transparent electrodes,¹¹⁻¹⁴ heating elements,^{15, 16} wearable electronics,¹⁷ battery and capacitor electrodes,^{5, 18, 19} sensors,²⁰ and EMI shields²¹⁻²³ while printed carbon nanotube networks have shown applications as transistors,²⁴ LEDs,²⁵ and photodetectors.²⁶ More recently, solution-deposited networks of 2D materials such as graphene and MoS₂ have been examined for use in a wide range of fields from (opto)electronics to energy storage.²⁷⁻³¹ Many of these applications require the maximisation of the conductivity or mobility of the nanoparticle networks (nanonets).

It is important to study the details of charge transport in such networks, both to further our understanding of the physics of the conduction mechanisms and to facilitate the maximisation of the electrical performance of such networks. However, standard methods for studying charge transport mechanisms, such as the measurement of conductivity and/or mobility as a function of temperature, do not give a complete picture of electrical conduction in these systems. This is because charge carriers traversing a nanonet must alternate between two modes of conduction; intra- and inter-particle charge transport.³²⁻³⁴ Clearly, carriers must spend some time travelling through the nanoparticles (intra-particle transport). This might be via bandlike transport in ordered materials or via hopping in disordered or defective ones. However, after travelling through a nanoparticle, it will always be necessary for the carrier to transit to the next nanoparticle, i.e. to cross a particle-particle junction. We refer to this as inter-particle transport and, in most cases^{27, 34} it will be via hopping or tunnelling (but not always, see below). Movement of carriers over long distances in nanonets will always involve alteration between intra- and inter-particle transport. This means the basic unit of resistance associated with a nanonet is R_J+R_N where R_N is the resistance of the (average) nanoparticle and R_J is the

resistance of the (average) junction.³² Thus, because temperature-dependent resistivity measurements probe R_J+R_N , it is difficult to separate the effects of intra- and inter-particle charge transport.

Usually, nanonets display network conductivity and mobility that tend to be at least an order of magnitude below that of the component nanoparticles.^{27, 34} It is usually assumed that this is because transport across junctions is rate-limiting i.e. $R_J \gg R_N$. This simplifies analysis of the temperature-dependence of network conductivity or mobility by allowing researchers to make the approximation that any mechanistic information contained in the data is associated with inter-particle transport. While this is probably true for most nano-networks today, it will not be the case as networks improve and junction resistances are reduced to the point where $R_J \sim R_N$.

To properly study the charge transport mechanism in nanonets, it is necessary to separately characterise both intra-particle and inter-particle charge transport mechanisms. Put simply, both R_J and R_N must be measured together as a function of temperature (or magnetic field or gate voltage etc). The first steps in this direction have been demonstrated recently. We have recently described a method³² based on impedance spectroscopy to simultaneously measure R_J and R_N as a function of temperature in networks of semiconducting MoS₂ nanosheets.

However, this impedance-based method is probably not applicable to networks of metallic or semi-metallic nanoparticles. This is because such systems are expected to have relatively low junction resistances,³² shifting the features of interest within the impedance spectrum out of the measurable frequency range (see S2 for further detail). Thus, an alternative method is required to simultaneously interrogate both intra- and inter-particle transport mechanisms in networks of conducting nanoparticles.

Here, we will demonstrate a simple method to measure the temperature dependence of R_N and R_J in conducting nanonets which cannot be interrogated using standard impedance spectroscopy. To do this, we measure the resistivity of conducting nano-particle networks at various temperatures for various nanoparticle sizes. We then use a simple model³² to extract R_N and R_J from the resistivity versus particle size data at each temperature. We demonstrate this method using spray coated networks of silver nanowires (AgNWs) as a model system. Silver nanowire (AgNW) networks have been heavily studied due to their excellent performance in various applications in the field of wearable technologies.^{11-13, 35-37} However, we use them here because the electrical properties of individual silver nanowires are well-defined and well-known. That is, their resistance is related to their resistivity via their

dimensions in a simple way while the resistivity of individual nanowires is reasonably close to the value of bulk silver in most cases.³⁸ In addition, their resistivity is not affected by environmental effects such as inadvertent doping in the way it is for other nanoparticles.³⁹ This means that one can easily benchmark the values of R_N extracted from our model with the literature in a way that would not be possible with other nanomaterials.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Length control and measurement of nanowire length

A key aspect of this work will be to measure the dependence of network resistivity on nanowire length. To achieve this, batches of nanowires of two different diameters were purchased from Novarials Corporation. SEM images of AgNWs deposited on substrates showed the nanowires to be long and uniform as shown in Figure 1A. Image analysis allowed the measurement of both the length and diameter with both parameters showing reasonably narrow distribution as shown in Figure 1B-C (see SI for all statistical data). The mean diameters, D_{NW} , of the two nanowire batches were $38\pm 1\text{nm}$ and $57\pm 1\text{nm}$, while the corresponding mean nanowire lengths, l_{NW} , were found to be $26.6\pm 1\mu\text{m}$ and $29.3\pm 1\mu\text{m}$ respectively (errors are standard errors of the mean).

The AgNWs were size-selected by sonicating the dispersions for various periods of time, a process known as sonication-induced scission^{16,40,41}. SEM images such as that shown in Figure 1D confirmed that this process results in shortening of the nanowires. This produced a range of fractions, each with a different mean nanowire length. SEM measurements (Figure 1E) showed the length to decrease with sonication time, from $26.6\mu\text{m}$ to $2.3\mu\text{m}$ for the 38nm diameter AgNWs and $29.3\mu\text{m}$ to $3.6\mu\text{m}$ for the 57nm diameter AgNWs. This fall-off in length with sonication time followed a power law, consistent with previously-observed behaviour.^{16,40,41} The data in Figure 1E is replotted in Figure 1F as the nanowire aspect ratio, l_{NW} / D_{NW} , plotted versus sonication time, t . This graph clearly demonstrates that the sonication data for both AgNW diameters converge onto a master curve consistent with $l_{NW} \propto D_{NW} \times t^n$, where $n=-0.66$. This exponent compares well to values of $n=-0.5$ obtained for SWCNTs⁴² and graphene⁴³ but differs somewhat from a previous report of $n=-0.34$ for AgNWs.⁴⁴

Network Characterisation

Nanowire networks were produced by spray-coating. Typically, networks were sprayed with an average thickness of ~500 nm; thick enough to avoid any percolative effects (i.e. thickness-dependent conductivity which occurs for network thicknesses below ~ 100 nm for AgNWs).⁴⁵ Spray coating produced disordered networks of randomly oriented nanowires as shown in Figure 2A-B. Such networks are also known to be highly porous with porosities of 80-90% typical.⁴⁶

The inter-nanowire junctions can be seen more clearly by visualising a sparse network using SEM (Figure 2C) or TEM (Figure 2D-E). These images show the junctions as consisting of nanowires in close contact. However, it is known that such as-produced nanowire junctions contain a layer of stabilising PVP polymer, which acts as an insulating barrier between the AgNWs, significantly hindering electron transport in as-produced AgNW networks, causing them to have a large network resistance. Thermal annealing has been shown to drastically reduce the network resistance by sintering the nanowires at the junctions and allowing the PVP layer to migrate.⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹ TEM images of individual junctions in AgNW networks after thermal annealing reveal dramatic changes in the junction morphology. In Figure 2E, post anneal, there is a clear welding at the junctions, suggesting displacement of the PVP layer. Overall, the TEM images show that the annealing process enhances the intimacy of the contact between the AgNWs at the junctions, helping to drastically reduce junction resistance and improve inter-nanowire transport. It also implies that the junctions themselves consist of metallic silver after annealing.

In order to quantify the morphology of these networks, we performed 3D imaging via nanotomography. As described in ref⁴⁶, 3D imaging of nano-networks can be achieved using a combination of repeated focused ion beam milling and scanning electron microscopy (FIB-SEM). After the appropriate image segmentation, this procedure yields a large set of 2D images where each pixel is labelled via its material composition. These images can then be combined to generate a 3D image where each voxel represents (in our case) either free space (part of a pore) or silver (part of a nanowire). Typically, such 3D images have resolution of 5 nm in the image plane and 15 nm out of plane, i.e. the voxel size is 5nm×5nm×15nm.

Examples of 3D images collected for the nanowire networks under study here are shown in Figure 3. In principle, such images contain all structural and morphological information relating to the network which is available at the resolution of the image. This includes

parameters relating to nanowire orientation as well as pore size and shape etc. However, for our purposes, the most important available information relates to the network porosity (P_{Net}) because of its effect on the network resistivity (see below). Using the methods described in ref⁴⁶ we have calculated mean network porosities of $P_{Net}=85\pm5\%$ for networks of AgNWs with $D_{NW}=38$ nm and $P_{Net}=89\pm3\%$ for networks of AgNWs with $D_{NW}=57$ nm.

Length dependence

We recently demonstrated³² that the resistivity, ρ_{Net} , of a network of 1D nanowires (or nanotubes) is related to the resistivity of the nanowires themselves, ρ_{NW} , by:

$$\rho_{Net} \approx \frac{1}{(1-P_{Net})} \left[\rho_{NW} + \frac{\pi D_{NW}^2 R_J}{2l_{NW}} \right] \left[1 + \frac{8}{n_{NW} l_{NW} \pi D_{NW}^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

where P_{Net} , D_{NW} , l_{NW} and n_{NW} are mean values of network porosity, nanowire diameter, nanowire length and nanowire carrier concentration, respectively. In the case of conducting nanomaterials such as AgNWs, n_{NW} is very large, meaning final term of this equation becomes negligible:

$$\rho_{Net} \approx \frac{1}{(1-P_{Net})} \left[\rho_{NW} + \frac{\pi D_{NW}^2 R_J}{2l_{NW}} \right] \quad (2)$$

This equation predicts that measuring the network resistivity (ρ_{Net}) as a function of AgNW length (l_{NW}) will allow the extraction R_{NW} and R_J by fitting, once P_{Net} and D_{NW} are known. The introduction of this equation serves as a foundational framework for our analyses, providing a quantitative basis for the determination of the role of junctions in AgNW networks.

To investigate the effect of nanowire length on the electrical properties of the network, we used the length-selected nanowire dispersions produced above to fabricate a set of networks with various nanowire lengths. We then measured the network conductivity, σ_{Net} , using 4-probe techniques. Figure 4A-B shows σ_{Net} , measured for both nanowire diameters, as a function of the mean length of nanowires making up the network, l_{NW} . These graphs both appear to scale roughly linearly with AgNW length as previously observed by Sorel et al.⁴⁴. It is also worth noting that our most conductive networks display conductivities approaching 5×10^6 S/m, competitive with the best metallic nanowire networks^{13, 48, 49} and to our knowledge surpassed only by networks of silver nanosheets.⁵⁰

However, we note that Equation 2 predicts the network resistivity, ρ_{Net} , to scale linearly with the inverse of nanowire length. Plotting the data as ρ_{Net} versus $1/l_{NW}$ in Figure 4C-D shows straight lines for both nanowire diameters. Linear fitting allows us to extract values for ρ_{NW} and R_J for each nanowire type. We obtained values of $\rho_{NW}=1.5\pm0.7\times10^{-8}$ Ω m and $\rho_{NW}=0.6\pm0.3\times10^{-8}$ Ω m for the 38nm and 57nm AgNW networks, respectively. These values are broadly consistent with the resistivity of bulk silver ($\rho_{Ag}=1.6\times10^{-8}$ Ω m), supporting the validity of our approach. The higher resistivity observed for the 38nm nanowires is consistent with expected size-dependent surface scattering effects in smaller diameter nanowires⁵¹.

In addition, the junction resistances determined from our study are $R_J=265\pm40$ Ω and $R_J=124\pm22$ Ω for the 38nm and 57nm AgNW networks, respectively. The junction resistance increases for smaller diameter nanowires due to the reduced contact area at the junction interface. These data are consistent with a wide range of values of R_J reported by Forro et al.³⁸ for silver and copper nanowire networks which mostly cluster in the range $50\Omega < R_J < 2$ k Ω . This range is also consistent with a number of other studies which have reported R_J values from 11 Ω to 2 k Ω .⁵²⁻⁵⁶ The wide range of reported R_J values may be attributed to the wide range of possible junction morphologies. Such a broad range of junction types is expected due to variations of nanowire diameter and, more importantly, annealing conditions.

We can use the known dimensions of our AgNWs, combined with the nanowire resistivities to estimate the nanowire resistances, R_{NW} . To do this, we assume that carriers travel, on average, through half the length of each nanowire,³² leading to $R_{NW} = \rho_{NW}(l_{NW} / 2) / (\pi D_{NW}^2 / 4)$. This allowed us to calculate R_{NW}/R_J , a parameter that determines how junction-limited each network is, for each of our nanowire fraction. We found values of R_{NW}/R_J ranging from 0.06 to 0.7 for the $D_{NW}=38$ nm AgNW networks and from 0.03 to 0.26 for the $D_{NW}=57$ nm AgNW networks. We note that almost all networks studied here have $R_{NW}/R_J < 1$, showing them to be predominantly junction limited.

Temperature Dependence of AgNW network resistivity

Measurement of the temperature dependence of a material's conductivity, resistivity or mobility is a powerful tool for identifying the dominant conductive mechanisms present in the sample. A number of studies have reported the temperature dependence of the conductivity or resistivity of various solution processed networks, including those comprising AgNWs,⁵⁷ carbon nanotubes,⁵⁸ graphene,^{59,60} and semiconducting 2D materials such as MoS₂.^{59,61} In each

case the results reflect the temperature dependence of the rate limiting step in the conduction process, most likely charge transport across junctions. The ability to differentiate the contributions of intraparticle transport (e.g. through the nanowires) from interparticle transport (e.g. across junctions) to the network's overall conductivity would allow us to individually examine both intraparticle and interparticle conduction mechanisms at the same time. By separating the contributions of these two components, we can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the conduction mechanisms operating within the network.

Here, we achieve this by measuring the temperature-dependence of the network resistivity for networks comprising nanowires of different lengths. We note that for technical reasons we used two-probe rather than 4-probe measurements, meaning our resistivity values are slightly overestimated. However, this does not affect the general validity of the method. Figure 5 A and B shows the temperature dependence of the resistivity of AgNW networks for three different nanowire lengths each for AgNWs with $D_{NW}=38$ nm and $D_{NW}=57$ nm respectively. The data shows that the network resistivity increases with increasing temperature, as is characteristic of metallic materials. Such data has been reported before by various authors.^{57, 59}

Our novel contribution is to replot this data, not as ρ_{Net} versus T for various nanowire lengths, but to plot ρ_{Net} versus $1/\langle l_{NW} \rangle$ for various temperatures (Figure 5C-D). This allows us to fit the data for each temperature using Equation 2 as we did above. In this way, values of R_J and ρ_{NW} can be extracted for each temperature (Figure 5E-F). This allows us to examine the temperature dependence of R_J and ρ_{NW} individually, which enables the separate examination of intra-nanowire and inter-nanowire conduction mechanisms.

Figure 5E shows the extracted ρ_{NW} vs temperature data extracted from our AgNW networks as well as literature data for ρ_{NW} vs temperature measured on individual AgNWs for comparison. We find our ρ_{NW} data (extracted from network measurements) to be consistent to the published data measured on individual nanowires.^{62, 63}

The temperature dependence of individual AgNWs has been extensively studied. It is well understood that, within certain limitations,⁶² it can be described by a combination of the Bloch-Grüneisen (BG) formula:⁶²⁻⁶⁴

$$\rho(T) = \rho_0 + \rho_{e-ph}(T) \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_{e-ph} = \alpha_{e-ph} \left(\frac{T}{\Theta_D} \right)^5 \times \int_0^{\Theta_D/T} \frac{x^5}{(e^x - 1)(1 - e^{-x})} dx \quad (4)$$

where ρ_0 is the residual resistivity due to defect scattering, ρ_{e-ph} is the resistivity arising from electron-phonon (e-ph) interactions, α_{e-ph} is a constant characterising e-ph coupling and Θ_D is the Debye temperature. Equation 4 assumes that the dominant source of temperature dependence is the scattering of electrons by phonons and predicts that the resistivity of a material increases with increasing temperature. This is because the increased thermal energy allows the phonons to scatter electrons more effectively, which reduces the mean free path of electrons.

Our $\rho_{NW}(T)$ data shows a good fit to the BG equation over our temperature range (Figure 5E), which confirms that the primary mode of scattering in our AgNWs is due to phonons. The Debye temperature for AgNWs with $D_{NW}=38$ nm and $D_{NW}=57$ nm were found to be 181 K and 133 K, respectively, which aligns well with the reported range of 128-215 K for AgNWs⁶²⁻⁶⁴ and demonstrating the expected higher Debye temperature for smaller nanowires.^{63, 64} The extracted residual resistivities were $8.9 \times 10^{-9} \Omega \text{ m}$ for the 38nm nanowires and $4.8 \times 10^{-9} \Omega \text{ m}$ for the 57 nm nanowires, both consistent with the typical reported range of 1.7×10^{-9} - $2.0 \times 10^{-8} \Omega \text{ m}$ for AgNWs⁶²⁻⁶⁴ and consistent with previously reported nanowire diameter scaling.⁶³ Additionally, the electron-phonon coupling constants were determined to be $9.6 \times 10^{-8} \Omega \text{ m}$ and $3.0 \times 10^{-8} \Omega \text{ m}$ for the $D_{NW}=38$ nm and $D_{NW}=57$ nm AgNWs, respectively, which also scale with D_{NW} as expected⁶³ and fall within the reported range of 3.5×10^{-8} - $9.9 \times 10^{-8} \Omega \text{ m}$.⁶²⁻⁶⁴ This clearly shows that the $\rho_{NW}(T)$ data extracted using our method is consistent both with other reported experimental data and with the standard theoretical framework (the BG equation) used to analyse such data.

A plot of R_I vs temperature is shown in Figure 5F. The data are quite linear in T, consistent with metallic behaviour at temperatures above the Debye temperature. We interpret this as meaning the junctions consist of silver welds as previously reported for annealed networks.⁶⁵ ⁶⁶ However, this linearity, coupled with the limited temperature range, makes it impossible to apply the BG fit accurately. Nevertheless, we can roughly analyse the data by taking the high temperature approximation to equation 4 (expanding the exponentials to first order and integrating) which yields:

$$\rho = \rho_0 + \frac{\alpha_{e-ph}}{4\Theta_D} T \quad (5)$$

We then assume that the junction resistance can be related to the resistivity of the material making up the junctions via $R_j = \rho / b$. Here b is a parameter with dimensions of length which describes the geometric properties of the junction. We can then write:

$$R_j = \frac{\rho_0}{b} + \frac{\alpha_{e-ph}}{4b\Theta_D} T \quad (6)$$

We estimate b by comparing the values for junction resistance and nanowire resistivity at room temperature yielding $b=1.65 \times 10^{-10}$ m and $b=2.18 \times 10^{-10}$ m for the 38 nm and 57 nm diameter nanowires respectively.

We can use Equation 6 to fit the data in figure 5F. From the intercepts we find the residual resistivities to be 1.9×10^{-8} Ω m for the 38nm nanowires and 7.7×10^{-9} Ω m for the 57 nm nanowires, both consistent with the values extracted from the ρ_{NW} data. From the slopes, we find the ratio of the electron-phonon coupling and the Debye temperature, α_{e-ph} / Θ_D , obtaining values of 3.8×10^{-10} ΩmK^{-1} and 1.9×10^{-10} ΩmK^{-1} , for the 38 nm and 57 nm diameter nanowires respectively, close to the values of 5.3×10^{-10} ΩmK^{-1} and 2.3×10^{-10} ΩmK^{-1} found from the ρ_{NW} data. This result shows that the temperature dependence of our junction resistance values is fully consistent with the expected behavior of metallic silver junctions. We reiterate that such metallic junctions are expected to occur in annealed networks of silver nanowires such as those used here.⁶⁵ These results fully support the effectiveness of our method to extract both nanowire and junction resistance from length-dependent network resistivity measurements.

CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a broadly applicable method for the extraction of the temperature dependent nanoparticle resistivity and junction resistance in printed nanomaterial networks, using AgNWs as a model system. By employing a nanowire length dependent study, we determined that the junction resistance is the primary bottleneck in the charge transport within these AgNW networks, with networks exhibiting $R_{NW}/R_j < 1$. Repeating these measurements at various temperatures allows us to extract both nanowire resistivity as well as junction resistance

as a function of temperature. Both parameters followed Bloch-Grüneisen behaviour, consistent with metallic conduction in both nanowires and junctions.

Our work emphasises the importance of understanding the role of junctions and nanoparticles for the optimisation of nanomaterial networks. We establish a framework for the in-depth analysis of the charge transport in nanomaterial networks which enables future work to focus on exploring ways to further optimise ρ_{NP} and R_J for improved performance in practical applications. We anticipate that this method will be used for analysis of other technologically relevant systems such as networks of semiconducting or metallic carbon nanotubes.

EXPERIMENTAL

AgNW Network Production

Silver nanowire stock dispersions (A40 40 nm \times 35 μ m in 2-propanol and A60 60nm \times 45 μ m in 2-propanol) were sourced from Novarials Corporation. The AgNWs were size-selected using sonication induced scission in an ultrasonic bath. In each case a stock AgNW dispersion was sonicated for a fixed duration at a concentration of 1 mg mL⁻¹ in IPA. Sonication times of 0.05, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 hours were used to produce the size-selected AgNW inks. Spray coating was carried out at a AgNW concentration of 0.5 mg mL⁻¹ using a Harder and Steenbeck Infinity CRplus Airbrush attached to a computer-controlled Janome JR2300N mobile gantry. All deposited traces were defined using stainless steel shadow masks producing a serpentine pattern with a channel length of 97mm and channel width of 500 μ m. Fused silica substrates were used due to their low roughness. An N2 back pressure of 45 psi, nozzle diameter of 400 μ m and stand-off distance of 100 mm between the nozzle and substrate were used⁶⁷. The networks were then annealed at a temperature of 135°C to reduce R_J by sintering the junctions.

Microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the printed nanosheet networks was performed using a Carl ZEISS Ultra Plus SEM. Samples were mounted on aluminium SEM stubs using conductive carbon tabs (Ted Pella) and grounded using conductive silver paint (PELCO, Ted Pella). All images were captured at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV using a working distance of 5 mm and a 30 μ m aperture. Both the In-lens and SE2 detectors were used for imaging.

Microscopy (TEM)

Bright-field transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was performed using a JEOL 2100 system operating at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Samples were diluted and drop-cast onto holey carbon grids (Agar Scientific) for imaging. The grids were placed on filter membranes to wick away excess solvent and dried overnight at 120 °C in a vacuum oven.

Electrical characterisation

Direct current (DC) electrical characterisation of the printed networks was performed in ambient conditions using a Keithley 2612A source-meter connected to a probe station. Four-terminal measurements were used to determine the resistance of the printed AgNW networks. The thickness of the deposited traces was determined using SEM cross-sections.

Temperature-dependent impedance:

The low frequency real component of the sample impedance was measured from a frequency of 1 Hz to 1000 Hz in the temperature range 20°C to -120°C using a broadband Alpha High-Resolution impedance Analyzer (Novocontrol GmbH, Germany), which utilizes a capacitance bridge technique to calculate impedance. The low frequency real impedance is expected to be identical to the DC resistance in samples such as these. The samples were placed inside a sample holder which has a fitted Pt 100 Ω resistance temperature sensor in contact with the electrodes. The temperature of the sample was controlled inside a double wall cryostat and maintained by a heated N₂ jet produced by evaporating liquid nitrogen inside a 50 litre dewar (Apollo 50 by Messer Griesheim GmbH). The Quatro temperature controller controls the power supplied to the dewar and gas heater. The AC measuring voltage applied to the sample was set at 0.5 V.

FIB-SEM Nanotomography

FIB-SEM nanotomography (FIB-SEM NT) was performed using a ZEISS Auriga dual-beam system and ATLAS 5 software (Version 5.3.3.31, ZEISS) as described in Ref.. All images were captured at a working distance of 5 mm using a 30 μm aperture and 2 kV accelerating voltage. Printed AgNW networks on glass microscope slides were directly mounted on aluminium stubs using conductive carbon tabs (Ted Pella Inc.) and grounded using silver paint (Ted Pella Inc.). Network cross-sections were milled using a 30 kV:600 pA gallium ion beam and imaged using both the In-lens and SE2 detectors. A slice thickness of 15 nm and in-plane pixel size of 5 nm were used to produce voxels 375 nm³ in size. The image stacks generated by the FIB-SEM NT run were aligned and interpolated using the sum of squared differences (SSD) matching

algorithm in Dragonfly (Version 2022.2.0.1409, Object Research Systems). To enable quantitative analysis, the greyscale network cross-sections (SE2 detector) were segmented into their nanowire and pore components using the trainable WEKA segmentation plugin⁶⁸ in FIJI⁶⁹. Prior to this the pixel intensity in each stack was normalised and the brightness and contrast were adjusted globally to maximise the difference between pore and nanowire pixels in FIJI. The two resulting image stacks contained only pore or AgNW pixels, which were then converted to 3D images representing both phases using Dragonfly. Network porosity was determined from the 3D volumes using both Taufactor⁷⁰ and FIJI⁶⁹.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION: Silver Nanowire Size Analysis, Discussion on the problems with the impedance spectroscopy method, Table comparing literature values for the Bloch-Grüneisen fitting parameters.

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FIGURES

Figure 1: **Material Characterisation.** **A)** SEM image of as-purchased AgNWs ($D_{NW}=38$ nm) deposited on Si/SiO₂. **B-C)** Example histograms showing the length (C) and diameter (D) distributions for the nanowires shown in A. Note: Full AgNW size analysis can be found in S1. **D)** SEM image of AgNWs ($D_{NW}=38$ nm) deposited on Si/SiO₂ after sonication for 2 hours. **E)** Mean length of AgNWs within each size-selected fraction as a function of sonication time. Data is shown for both $D_{NW}=38$ nm and $D_{NW}=57$ nm nanowires. **F)** Plot of $\langle l_{NW} \rangle / \langle D_{NW} \rangle$ as a function of sonication time showing data for all fractions over both nanowire diameters falls on a master curve.

Figure 2: **Network Characterisation.** **A)** SEM image of the top surface of stock length AgNW network with $D_{NW}=38\text{nm}$ nanowires. **B)** Typical cross-sectional SEM image of a AgNW network. **C)** High Magnification SEM image of typical junctions present within a AgNW network. **D)** TEM image of an unannealed AgNW-AgNW junction. **E)** TEM image of a completely annealed AgNW-AgNW junction showing sintering at the junction.

Figure 3: **Network 3D imaging.** FIB-SEM tomography images of sections of networks spray cast from silver nanowires with diameters of $D_{NW}=57\text{ nm}$ (**A**) and $D_{NW}=38\text{ nm}$ (**B**). The insets at the bottom right of each panel show small sections of individual cross-sectional SEMs.

Figure 4: **Dependence of network conductivity on AgNW length.** **A-B)** Conductivity of spray-cast AgNW networks, σ_{Nets} , versus mean nanowire length, l_{NW} , for AgNWs of diameter, D_{NW} , 38nm and 57nm, respectively. **C-D)** Resistivity of spray-cast AgNW networks, ρ_{Net} , versus the inverse of the mean nanowire length for AgNWs of diameter 38nm and 57nm, respectively. The line is a fit to Equation 2 which allows for the extraction of ρ_{NW} and R_J from the intercept and slope respectively.

Figure 5: **Temperature Dependence of AgNW networks.** **A-B)** Examples of network resistivity, ρ_{Net} , vs temperature for networks with various AgNW lengths for nanowires with $D_{NW}=38$ nm (A) and $D_{NW}=57$ nm (B). **C-D)** Examples of network resistivity, ρ_{Net} , measured at various temperatures plotted versus the inverse of the nanowire length, $\langle l_{NW} \rangle^{-1}$, for AgNWs of diameter 38nm (C) and 57nm (D). The lines are fits to Equation 1. **E)** The extracted nanowire resistivity plotted versus temperature for our AgNW networks compared to temperature dependent resistivity of individual silver nanowires reported in the literature^{62,63}. The lines are

a fit to equation 2 **F**) The extracted junction resistance versus temperature for our AgNW networks. The lines are fits to Equation 6.

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